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2 **DYNAMICAL DOWNSCALING OF CMIP6 SCENARIOS WITH ENEA-REG: AN**
3 **IMPACT-ORIENTED APPLICATION FOR THE MED-CORDEX REGION**
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31 **Keywords**

32 Regional Earth system models, Mediterranean climate, Marine Heatwaves, Sea level height,
33 Med-CORDEX, Future scenario.

34 **Abstract**

35 In the framework of the coordinated regional modeling initiative Med-CORDEX (Coordinated
36 Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment), we present an updated version of the regional Earth
37 System Model ENEA-REG designed to downscale, over the Mediterranean basin, the models
38 used in the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP6). The regional ESM includes
39 coupled atmosphere (WRF), ocean (MITgcm), land (Noah-MP, embedded within WRF), and
40 river (HD) components with spatial resolution of 12 km for the atmosphere, 1/12° for the ocean
41 and 0.5° for the river rooting model.

42 For the present climate, we performed a hindcast (i.e. reanalysis-driven) and a historical
43 simulation (GCM-driven) over the 1980-2014 temporal period. The evaluation shows that the
44 regional ESM reliably reproduces the mean state, spatial and temporal variability of the relevant
45 atmospheric and ocean variables.

46 In addition, we analyze the future evolution (2015-2100) of the Euro-Mediterranean climate
47 under three different scenarios (SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, SSP5-8.5), focusing on several relevant
48 essential climate variables and climate indicators for impacts. Among others, results highlight
49 how, for the scenarios SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5, the intensity, frequency and duration of marine
50 heat waves continue to increase until the end of the century and anomalies of up to 2°C, which
51 are considered extreme at the beginning of this century, will become the norm in less than a
52 hundred years under the SSP5-8.5 scenario.

53 Overall, our results demonstrate the improvement due to the high-resolution air-sea coupling for
54 the representation of high impact events, such as marine heat waves, and sea-level height.

55

56 **1. Introduction**

57 Although global climate models (GCMs) and Earth system models (ESMs) represent an
58 important source of climate information for the regional scale, regional climate models (RCMs)
59 allow to better represent the complex phenomena that emerge at higher resolutions, especially
60 over regions of complex orography or with heterogeneous surface characteristics, such as the
61 Mediterranean basin (Doblas-Reyes et al. 2021). As matter of fact, the last IPCC
62 (Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change) Assessment Report (AR) acknowledged that
63 regional climate information for impacts and risk assessment is increasingly robust and mature to
64 feed climate services and impacts studies with the higher resolution they need (Ranasinghe et al.
65 2021). On the other hand, local information on climate change impacts produced by global
66 models should be considered with some caution (Gualdi et al. 2013).

67 In the Mediterranean region, the climate is characterized by the interplay between midlatitude
68 and subtropical circulation regimes (Tuel and Eltahir 2020) with local air–sea interactions that
69 can substantially influence the regional climate and the Mediterranean Sea circulation (Somot et
70 al. 2008; Artale et al. 2010; Somot et al. 2018). Moreover, the Mediterranean basin is a well-
71 known hot-spot region for climate change (Giorgi 2006; Tuel and Eltahir 2020, Cos et al. 2022)
72 and, due to both its conformation and the distribution of the population over its territory, it is
73 particularly vulnerable to both hydrogeological risks (heavy rainfall, landslides, flooding) and
74 coastal risks (sea level rise, marine heat waves) with effects on the health and economies of
75 communities. Hence, predicting the effects and extent of climate change over this region has
76 important implications for natural ecosystems (Ciais et al. 2005) and millions of people already
77 exposed to heat waves and water-stressed conditions (Michetti et al. 2022). Furthermore,
78 understanding and predicting the effects of climate change allows to improve the methodologies
79 for prevention, adaptation and mitigation strategies.

80 For these reasons, different regional climate models have been developed and used to study both
81 present and future Mediterranean climate systems (e.g., Dubois et al. 2012; Ruti et al. 2016;
82 Darmaraki et al. 2019; Parras-Berrocal et al. 2020; Soto-Navarro et al. 2020; Reale et al 2022)
83 within a Coordinated Regional Climate Downscaling Experiment (CORDEX) protocol ensuring
84 that model simulations are carried out under similar conditions (Giorgi and Gutowski 2015).
85 Indeed, to be relevant and useful for decision-making, climate information must rely on multiple
86 lines of evidence, based on ensembles of different models and on data-based process
87 understanding (Doblas-Reyes et al. 2021).

88 In the framework of the CORDEX program, regional climate model simulations dedicated to the
89 Mediterranean area belong to the Med-CORDEX initiative (Ruti et al. 2016). One of the
90 objectives of this initiative is to explicitly represent the intense air-sea interactions that
91 characterize the Mediterranean region, by developing ocean-atmosphere coupled models aimed
92 at improving the performance of local information at climatological scales and provide reliable
93 future projections.

94 The ability of regional models to reliably reproduce the observed changes in mean and extreme
95 temperature and precipitation over the Euro-Mediterranean region is widely documented (e.g.
96 Kotlarski et al. 2014; Katragkou et al. 2015; Gutiérrez et al. 2021). In particular, hindcast (i.e.
97 analyses-driven) experiments, conducted within the Euro-CORDEX (Jacob et al. 2014) and
98 Med-CORDEX (Ruti et al. 2016) coordinated initiatives demonstrated the capability of
99 reproducing both the main characteristics of Euro-Mediterranean climate and the local

100 circulation features (Cardoso and Soares 2022; Drobinski et al. 2018) at resolutions ranging
101 between 12 and 25 km (Kotlarski et al. 2014; Fantini et al. 2018). Furthermore, regional models
102 provide improved resolution of the spatial patterns and seasonal cycles of precipitation, including
103 extremes (e.g., Heikkilä et al. 2011; Giorgi and Gutowski 2015).

104 The results of these coordinated regional modelling initiatives have allowed the scientific
105 community to define a number of climatic quantities that are relevant to socio-economic sectors
106 and natural systems (Ranasinghe et al. 2021). Additionally, the Global Climate Observing
107 System (GCOS - <https://gcos.wmo.int/en/home>) developed the concept of essential climate
108 variables (ECVs), namely relevant parameters for the characterization of Earth's climate. ECVs
109 can be either physical, chemical or biological, single or grouped (due to their joint concurrence
110 in determining critical processes). They provide reliable, traceable, observation-based evidence
111 that enables the accurate modelling and prediction that support policy development and
112 adaptation planning, by helping scientists understand the drivers of past, current, and future
113 climate variability (GCOS 2016). ECVs also provide a benchmark for climate model validation
114 and guidance as to the essential variables that should constitute the standard output of any
115 numerical experiment. Among ECVs, temperature and precipitation are known to affect a wide
116 variety of processes and systems, with important consequences for natural ecosystems and
117 human society.

118 Similarly, the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS - <https://www.goosocean.org/>), defined a
119 list of critical variables (Essential Ocean Variables, i.e. EOVs). Among EOVs, sea level height
120 integrates several complex processes, whose interaction can dramatically affect coastal
121 ecosystems and communities under a changing climate. The sea level rise under future scenarios
122 represents a risk for people, coastal ecosystems, and infrastructure, particularly in the
123 Mediterranean basin where millions of people live on coastal areas (Carillo et al. 2011; Sannino
124 et al. 2022). Similarly, rising Sea Surface Temperatures (SST) can also significantly affect the
125 current equilibrium of our oceans, as well as several economic activities that traditionally exploit
126 marine resources.

127 Within the Med-CORDEX initiative, we developed an improved version of the regional Earth
128 system model ENEA-REG (Anav et al. 2021) specifically designed to downscale the models of
129 the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP6) (Eyring et al. 2016) over the
130 Mediterranean basin. CMIP6 is the latest phase of the World Climate Research Programme
131 (WCRP) initiative, aimed at improving our understanding of past, present and future climate

132 changes related to natural variability and anthropogenic radiative forcing, in a multi-model
133 framework.

134 In the following sections, we first assess the skills of ENEA-REG in reproducing present climate
135 conditions in terms of relevant ECVs and EOVs. Validation is performed by comparing results
136 from a historical simulation (i.e., regional ESM forced by global ESM simulation) with those of
137 a hindcast experiment (i.e., regional ESM forced with reanalysis data) and a set of observational-
138 based and reanalysis datasets to assess model performances and identify possible shortcomings
139 of the regional ESM. Then, we show climate projections under three different scenarios and, as
140 an example of the added value for impact studies, we present an analysis of marine heatwaves in
141 the simulated scenarios. In fact, the high-resolution coupling between the atmospheric and the
142 oceanic model is expected to affect the behavior of extreme events implying energy and mass
143 fluxes which are, at the same time, intense and localized geographically, particularly in the
144 Mediterranean basin (e.g., Lebeaupin-Brossier et al. 2015). As marine heatwaves are expected to
145 increase in frequency and intensity under climate change (Darmaraki et al. 2019), understanding
146 their future occurrence under different climate scenarios is fundamental to assess the impacts on
147 marine ecosystems and prevent financial losses associated to fish mortality.

148

149 **2. Model description and experiment design**

150 The ENEA-REG (Anav et al. 2021) is a regional ESM comprising multiple modeling
151 components, namely the atmosphere, ocean, land, and river routing, designed for high-resolution
152 climate studies and applications. The data exchange, regridding, and interpolation among model
153 components are facilitated by the utilization of the RegESM coupler, as detailed in Turuncoglu
154 (2019). RegESM is based on the Earth System Modeling Framework (ESMF) library,
155 specifically version 7.1, and the NUOPC (National Unified Operational Prediction Capability)
156 layer to establish interconnections, synchronization, and horizontal grid interpolation among the
157 various model components.

158 ENEA-REG is based on the Weather Research and Forecasting (WRF version 4.2.2, Skamarock
159 et al. 2008) to simulate the atmosphere dynamic, the Massachusetts Institute of Technology
160 General Circulation Model (MITgcm version z67; Marshall et al. 1997) to represent the ocean
161 state and circulation, while the Hydrological Discharge (HD version 1.0.2, Hagemann and
162 Dümenil 1998; Hagemann and Dümenil-Gates 2001) model is used to simulate freshwater fluxes
163 over the land surface and to provide a river discharge to the ocean model.

164 Compared to the version described in Anav et al. (2021), here we use an updated WRF version
165 that employs hybrid vertical levels instead of sigma-p vertical coordinates. Moreover, we have
166 implemented the microphysics and cumulus parameterization proposed by Morrison et al. (2009)
167 and Janjić et al. (1994), respectively. Considering the ocean component, the main improvement
168 is in the ocean boundary conditions over the Atlantic box out of Gibraltar strait: here we use
169 monthly mean sea level change and tracers (temperature and salinity) profiles both applied with a
170 classical sponge layer formulation.

171 As in Anav et al. (2021), the atmospheric and the ocean model exchange sea surface temperature
172 (SST), surface pressure, wind components, freshwater (evaporation – precipitation) and heat
173 fluxes. Unlike the previous version, here the net heat flux is computed from net longwave, net
174 shortwave, latent heat, and sensible heat fluxes, while we provide the shortwave radiation as a
175 separate term able to penetrate the ocean. Furthermore, the hydrological model uses surface and
176 sub-surface runoff, provided by WRF, to compute the river discharge and exchanges this field
177 with the ocean component to close the water cycle. The coupling time step between the ocean
178 and the atmosphere is set to 3-hours, while the coupling with the hydrological model is set to 1-
179 day

180 The model domain covers the Med-CORDEX region, as shown in **Figure 1**. The horizontal
181 resolution of the atmospheric and ocean components is 12 km and $1/12^\circ$ (approximately 10 km)
182 respectively, while the river routing model is implemented on a regular grid of 0.5° .

183 In this study we have performed a hindcast simulation initialized and forced through ERA5
184 (Hersbach et al. 2020) and ORAS5 (Zuo et al. 2019) reanalysis for the atmospheric and ocean
185 components, respectively. In addition, an historical and three CMIP6 global scenario simulations
186 (SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5, SSP5-8.5, Eyring et al. 2016; O'Neill et al. 2016) have been downscaled;
187 in particular we have selected the CMIP6 MPI-ESM1-2-HR (Gutjahr et al. 2019) as driving
188 model that is characterized by the following configuration: T127 (0.93° or ~ 103 km) for the
189 atmosphere and TP04 (0.4° or ~ 44 km) for the ocean.

190 Among all the available CMIP6 models, in addition to the relatively high spatial resolution, we
191 selected the MPI-ESM1.2-HR as it has a well-balanced radiation budget and its climate
192 sensitivity is explicitly tuned to 3 K (Müller et al. 2018), making this model well suited for
193 prediction and impact studies. Both the present-climate experiments cover the period 1st August
194 1980-31st December 2014, while future climate simulations span the period 2015-2100.

195 In general, ESMs exhibit various biases when compared to observations (Gleckler et al. 2008);
196 thus, when forcing a regional climate model with a global model, these biases could propagate

197 into regional simulations originating some regional biases and contributing to the uncertainties of
 198 climate projections (Dosio 2016). To overcome this problem, several bias corrections techniques
 199 can be applied to the forcing data before using them for the dynamical downscaling. Here, we do
 200 not perform any bias correction to the high frequency lateral boundary conditions (i.e., 6h) of the
 201 MPI-ESM1-2-HR atmospheric component, while monthly salinity, temperature and elevation
 202 used as open boundary conditions for the MITgcm model are bias-corrected.

203 This different approach among ocean and atmospheric variables is due to the peculiar
 204 Mediterranean thermohaline circulation, which is extremely sensitive to the variations of
 205 temperature and salinity fields, even those penetrating from the lateral boundary conditions
 206 through the narrow Gibraltar Strait (Pinardi and Mosetti 2000). Thus, in order to avoid any
 207 incorrect or unrealistic evolution of the Mediterranean circulation, induced by a spurious heat
 208 and salt content coming from the biased CMIP6, it is advisable to remove the bias of the forcing
 209 data (Med-CORDEX protocol, <https://zenodo.org/record/8210985>), considering also that an
 210 altered Mediterranean Sea circulation, caused by the poor quality of the lateral boundary
 211 conditions, could not be easily recovered through different a-posteriori bias correction techniques
 212 of the simulated marine fields.

213 The bias correction applied to the ocean variables follows the approach proposed by Bruyère et
 214 al. (2014) which corrects the mean bias of the driving model keeping the original interannual
 215 variability and trends. Following this approach, the monthly data are decomposed into a mean
 216 seasonally varying climatological component (\overline{ESM}) plus a perturbation term (ESM'):

217

$$218 \quad ESM = \overline{ESM} + ESM' \quad 1)$$

219

220 Similarly, the ORAS5 reanalysis data are broken down into a seasonally varying mean
 221 climatological component (\overline{Obs}) and a perturbation term (Obs'):

222

$$223 \quad Obs = \overline{Obs} + Obs' \quad 2)$$

224

225 The bias-corrected MPI-ESM1-2-HR boundary conditions (ESM^{bc}) are then constructed by
 226 replacing the climatological mean from Eq. 1 with the climatological mean of the reanalysis
 227 computed from Eq. 2:

228

$$229 \quad ESM^{bc} = \overline{Obs} + ESM' \quad 3)$$

230 3. Validation of ENEA-REG components

231 3.1 Present climate representation as simulated by the atmospheric model

232 To analyze the performance of the regional ESM in reproducing the mean annual cycle of
233 surface air temperature, in Figure 2 we compare box plots of seasonal mean temperatures from
234 the hindcast and historical ENEA-REG downscaling experiments with ERA5 data. In addition to
235 the temperature simulated by the regional model we also show the driving model (MPI-ESM1.2-
236 HR) and the ensemble mean of 25 CMIP6 ESMs. Means, medians, and percentiles, computed for
237 the temporal period 1982–2014, are spatially aggregated over the different subdomains employed
238 for model diagnostics in the regional climate change project PRUDENCE (Christensen and
239 Christensen 2007).

240 In general, the downscaling experiments reproduce quite well the seasonal temperature
241 climatology for most of the PRUDENCE regions, although some large biases are found in some
242 domains and seasons. In particular, the largest differences between ENEA-REG and ERA5 occur
243 during winter (DJF, December-January-February) in Eastern Europe (i.e., EA subdomain) where
244 the model shows a cold bias ($-2.3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) in both simulations. During summer (JJA, June-July-
245 August) the downscaling experiments are systematically warmer than the reference data in
246 several subdomains with the most pronounced bias occurring in the Alpine region ($1.6\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the
247 hindcast and $1.1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for the historical) and over Eastern Europe ($1.9\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ in the hindcast and $1.5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$
248 for the historical). Considering the other seasons, during spring (MAM, March-April-May) the
249 hindcast simulation does not exhibit any relevant bias (maximum cold bias of $0.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ found in
250 mid-Europe), while the historical simulation exhibits a cold bias larger than -1°C in several
251 subdomains (i.e., Alps, Eastern Europe, France, and Mid-Europe). Similarly, in fall (SON,
252 September-October-November) the hindcast simulation is in good agreement with reference data
253 (the largest biases are found over Eastern Europe $-0.4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ and mid-Europe $-0.3\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), while the
254 historical experiment is systematically colder than ERA5 in all the sub-regions, with the larger
255 bias occurring in mid-Europe ($-1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). In this latter case, the cold bias in these domains seems to
256 be inherited by the driving MPI-ESM1.2-HR global model. Considering the CMIP6 models, it is
257 widely known that, in terms of biases, the multi-model ensemble mean often outperforms most
258 or all the individual ensemble members (e.g., Gleckler et al. 2008). Our results confirm that the
259 CMIP6 ensemble mean is, in general, closer to ERA5 than the single MPI-ESM1.2-HR model.
260 Noteworthy, in some regions (mostly in France, Iberian Peninsula and Mediterranean region) and
261 seasons the MPI-ESM1.2-HR displays large bias compared to the reference data, while its
262 downscaling performed with the ENEA-REG model is in good agreement with observations.

263 This result confirms that coarse global models perform poorly over the complex-terrain regions
264 surrounding the Mediterranean basin, while the downscaling of a global model produces more
265 reliable results.

266 The spatial variability of surface temperature simulated by ENEA-REG is assessed by means of
267 pattern correlations, computed over the PRUDENCE domains, using ERA5 as a reference
268 (Figure 3). Additionally, we have assessed the significance of pattern correlation difference
269 between the historical and the hindcast simulations (gray dot circles in Figure 3) and between the
270 historical and its driving global model (gray stars in Figure 3). The null hypothesis of getting the
271 same, or larger pattern correlation differences by chance, has been tested through a Monte Carlo
272 bootstrap procedure with 1000 repetitions. The method is based on building synthetic data
273 vectors by resampling with replacement the values of the two original series of grid points and
274 computing quantiles on the vector of differences between the synthetic series (Wilks 2011).
275 Results point out that the ENEA-REG historical and hindcast simulations are remarkably in
276 agreement with ERA5 data for all the domains, while the pattern correlations of the MPI-ESM1-
277 2-HR global model are always significantly lower, apart from EA in DJF. Besides, for several
278 sub-domains and seasons, we found no significant differences in the spatial patterns of surface
279 air temperature between the hindcast and historical simulations, while this latter is significantly
280 better than its forcing. This result suggests that the spatial patterns are more dependent on local
281 features and resolution than on the forcing used for the downscaling. This relevant improvement
282 of the dynamical downscaling with respect to its driving ESM can be explained by the
283 refinement of the spatial grid which is associated with a more realistic resolution of the non-
284 homogeneous surface characteristics, like the land cover, the complex orographic features, and
285 the land-sea contrast.

286 Model performance in reproducing inter-annual variability has been assessed by the Model
287 Variability Index (MVI, Gleckler et al. 2008); this metric provides a good measure to assess
288 standard deviation differences between model and reference data and allows to identify areas
289 with large biases in the magnitude of simulated variability. It is defined as:

290

$$291 \quad \text{MVI} = \left(\frac{\sigma_o}{\sigma_m} - \frac{\sigma_m}{\sigma_o} \right)^2 \quad 4)$$

292

293 where the grid-point standard deviations of the model and the observations are indicated by m
294 and o , respectively. The definition of a MVI threshold value that discriminates between “good”
295 and “bad” is somewhat arbitrary (Anav et al. 2013): Scherrer (2011) suggested a threshold of

296 0.5 as a good representation of inter-annual variability, while when model variability equals that
297 of the observations the MVI has a value of 0.

298 Seasonal MVI for the surface temperature (Figure 4) shows how the hindcast well reproduces the
299 observations variability in all the seasons. Conversely, the historical simulation tends to inherit
300 the variability reproduced by the global driving ESM, particularly in the seasons characterized by
301 a strong influence of the synoptic conditions (coming from the forcing at the boundaries). On the
302 other side, some improvements in MVI are evident over the Mediterranean region, particularly in
303 JJA, when local circulations and small-scale processes are better resolved by the regional ESM
304 than its driver, and during fall.

305 Looking at the Balkan region in DJF and Northern Africa in JJA, the historical simulation tends
306 to amplify the interannual variability of the global forcing. As also in the hindcast simulation
307 (see Figs. S.1, S.3, S.5 of supplementary material) these regions are characterized by an increase
308 (within 30%) of the variability with respect to the ERA5 dataset, this suggests that the problem
309 might be related to specific local processes' misrepresentation in the regional model. In particular,
310 the common patterns over Africa could be attributed to differences between time-varying
311 aerosols provided into ERA5 and the mean monthly climatology used in the ENEA-REG
312 simulations (Pavlidis et al. 2020). Similarly, considering the Balkan region, a possible
313 explanation for the poorer MVI during winter could be related to the interplay between the well-
314 known cold bias developing in the Eastern Europe (Figure 2, Mooney et al. 2013; Katragkou et
315 al. 2015; Anav et al. 2021) and the frequent North-Eastern outbreaks which transport cold air
316 masses and hence increases the temperature variability over this region. As pointed out by Varga
317 and Breuer (2020), this cold bias in winter is mainly caused by excessive snowfall and too
318 persistent snow cover; as we found a common behavior between the historical and hindcast
319 experiments (Figure 2), the local snow-albedo-temperature feedback could play a crucial role to
320 explain differences in temperature variability.

321 Consistent with the mean annual cycle of surface air temperature analysis, in Figure 5 we
322 compare box plots of seasonal mean precipitation from the two ENEA-REG downscaling
323 experiments with ERA5 data. During winter we found the hindcast experiment in good
324 agreement with ERA5 in all the sub-domains, with the largest dry bias of -0.2 mm/day occurring
325 in the Alpine and Mediterranean region. On the other side, the historical run, except over the
326 Mediterranean region, is systematically wetter than ERA5 and the largest biases are found over
327 the Alps (1.5 mm/day), France (1.3 mm/day) and Iberian Peninsula (1.1 mm/day). Similarly,
328 during MAM the hindcast is systematically drier than ERA5 in all the subdomains (largest bias

329 of -0.54 mm/day over Alps), while the historical is wetter and the largest discrepancies with
330 respect to ERA5 are found over France (0.76 mm/day) and the Alps (0.6 mm/day). During
331 summer, the hindcast and historical simulations are generally drier than ERA5 with the largest
332 biases found over the Alps for both the hindcast (-1.2 mm/day) and the historical (-0.75 mm/day).
333 Finally, during SON the two downscaling experiments agree well with ERA5 in all the sub-
334 regions and the most pronounced biases are found over the Alps in the hindcast (-0.58 mm/day)
335 and over France (0.67 mm/day) in the historical. The driving MPI-ESM1.2-HR model displays a
336 fairly good agreement with ERA5 data in most of the regions and seasons, with only France
337 during winter, (1.1 mm/day) and Alps during summer (-1.4 mm/day) showing a bias larger than
338 1 mm/day.

339 Figure 6 shows the pattern correlations for precipitation over the PRUDENCE domains. Results
340 are consistent with those of surface temperature, although the displayed values are generally
341 lower compared to those of Figure 3. In general, the correlations show values around 0.8 and the
342 poorest spatial agreement is found over the Alpine region for the historical experiment (0.5
343 during fall). Nevertheless, it is worth noting that in the same season and region the driving MPI-
344 ESM1-2-HR model has a null correlation with respect to ERA5 data. Looking at the maps of
345 precipitation (not shown), this discrepancy is caused by a spatial shift in rainfall patterns:
346 specifically, the coarse global model simulates a large rainfall northern the Alps, while in the
347 reanalysis the precipitation is more scattered around the mountains. Besides, it is evident how
348 results of the historical simulation are significantly different from MPI-ESM1-2-HR in all the
349 regions and seasons (except France during JJA) and the downscaling substantially improves the
350 spatial agreement with respect to ERA5.

351 The importance of improved resolution is particularly evident over the AL, EA and FR domains
352 while the improvement of the spatial patterns of precipitation over the MD domain may be
353 attributed also to the coupling with the high-resolution ocean model in ENEA-REG. This will be
354 further discussed in Section 3.2.

355 Figure 7 shows the MVI of precipitation. Excluding summer, where the near-zero precipitation
356 around the Mediterranean basin produces a MVI larger than 1, in all the remaining seasons we
357 found a fair agreement between the downscaling experiments and ERA5. Unlike surface
358 temperature, for precipitation the ENEA-REG tends to inherit the variability from the forcing for
359 all the seasons. In particular, the areas where the historical simulation shows the larger MVI are
360 the same where the global driving model has low performance. This is related to the resolution of
361 the regional model (12 km) which is still not able to resolve the atmospheric convective

362 structures (parameterized in our setup). Moving towards convection permitting resolutions is
363 expected to significantly improve precipitation variability, especially in the summer season.

364

365 **3.2 Present climate representation as simulated by the ocean model**

366 In this section, we focus on the validation of the ocean component of ENEA-REG in terms of its
367 capability of reproducing relevant fields, namely the EOVs, such as SST and sea level height,
368 together with the surface circulation and the hydrological structure of the basin.

369 Considering the SST, we compare mean seasonal climatologies from the hindcast and historical
370 ENEA-REG experiments with satellite-based observations
371 (SST_MED_SST_L4_REP_OBSERVATIONS_010_021); this latter is a daily, satellite retrieval
372 reconstruction of SST, with a spatial resolution of 0.05° that is available through the portal of the
373 Copernicus Marine Service (CMEMS; <https://marine.copernicus.eu/access-data>).

374 Figure 8 highlights a similar spatial distribution of the SST bias between the hindcast and the
375 historical simulations, although this latter is systematically colder than the hindcast. Besides,
376 both for the hindcast and for the historical run, the bias is positive during winter and negative in
377 summer, implying a reduction of the amplitude of the seasonal cycle of the downscaling
378 experiments with respect to the observations. On the other side, the driving global ESM exhibits
379 a less uniform pattern, with areas showing cold and warm biases during all the seasons; this is
380 likely due to the insufficient representation of small-scale features which promotes large local
381 differences with respect to satellite data.

382 Table 1 displays the vertical structure of temperature and salinity for the whole Mediterranean
383 (MED) basin and its western and eastern sub-basins (WMED; EMED); here we show averages
384 over three vertical layers (0-150 m, 150-600 m, 600-3500 m) for the reanalysis
385 (MEDSEA_MULTIYEAR_PHY_006_004 from the Copernicus Marine Service portal) as well
386 as the associated biases of the hindcast and historical simulations. In general, the results are in
387 good agreement with the reanalysis for both simulations. Considering the hindcast, it is warmer
388 than the reanalysis, except for a small negative anomaly in the EMED upper layer, while the
389 salinity is similar to the reference data in the western basin and slightly higher in the eastern. The
390 historical simulation agrees well with the hindcast, with a slightly reduced bias in the western
391 upper layer.

392 The average sea surface elevation and surface circulation, as simulated by the ENEA-REG, are
393 compared to satellite observations obtained from the $1/8^\circ$ resolution Mean Dynamic Topography
394 (MDT), which is representative of the mean dynamic component. MDT is computed using

395 satellite altimeter data and model results and is validated using independent observations (Rio et
396 al. 2014). Figure 9 shows a close spatial agreement between the ENEA-REG and satellite
397 observations, with the known permanent large-scale features well represented by the model. The
398 overall representation of large mesoscale features is satisfactory, even though some anticyclonic
399 anomalies in the Alborán Sea and in the Levantine are weaker than in the observations. In the
400 Aegean Sea, however, and particularly in its northern part, both simulations display elevation
401 anomalies smaller than in the observations; this local discrepancy will need to be further
402 investigated.

403 Looking at the simulated mean circulation (Figure 9), the hindcast and historical experiments
404 show a similar spatial pattern suggesting that the ENEA-REG is able to capture all the main
405 large-scale features of the geostrophic field already described in observation-based
406 reconstructions (Millot and Taupier-Letage 2005) and other numerical studies (Pinardi et al.
407 2015; Anav et al. 2021; Sannino et al. 2022). The stream of Atlantic water (AW) entering from
408 the Gibraltar Strait forms a meandering current along the North African coast, the Algerian
409 Current, which bifurcates in proximity of the Sicily Channel. A weaker current bordering the
410 Balearic Islands on the south side is also present in both experiments (Pinardi et al. 2015;
411 Sannino et al. 2022) but is not clearly visible in the geostrophic reconstruction associated to the
412 MDT. The two permanent cyclonic circulations that characterize the WMED, the wide gyre
413 formed by the Liguro-Provençal current and the Bonifacio cyclone, are present in the simulations,
414 and the two cyclonic structures occupying the central and southern portions of the Adriatic Sea
415 (e.g. Palma et al. 2020, and therein references) are well resolved. It is worth stressing that the
416 simulations correctly reproduce the circulation in the regions where deep and intermediate water
417 formation takes place: the Gulf of Lion, the southern Adriatic, and the Levantine Sea.

418 Besides, the comparison of the annual time series of the average basin elevation from the
419 hindcast with the observations (Figure 9) suggests that the reanalysis-driven simulation captures
420 the positive trend, the observed range of variation, and the main interannual variability in the
421 period 1993-2014; nevertheless, a large discrepancy is found in the first years of the 2000s, a
422 period characterized by strong atmospheric variability over the Mediterranean area.

423

424 **3.3 Marine heat waves**

425 Table 2 shows the performance of the ENEA-REG in reproducing the marine heatwaves in
426 specific sites of interest around the Mediterranean basin; the test sites are defined as pseudo-
427 rectangular areas of $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ centered around the locations listed in Table 2.

428 Different operational definitions of marine heatwaves have been adopted in past studies,
429 depending on the specific objectives. In general, heat waves should be characterized in terms of
430 their duration, intensity, and spatial extent. A systematic, hierarchical approach to defining
431 marine heat waves has been proposed by Hobday et al. (2016), who also introduced a specific
432 taxonomy (symmetric, fast onset, slow onset, low intensity, high intensity). Following Hobday et
433 al. (2016), the main features needed to define an heatwave are: (a) the identification of anomalies
434 compared to a climatology referred to specific times of the year; (b) the length of the heatwave
435 which is related to the specific process (e.g. ecological) of interest and (c) the possibility of
436 identifying well defined start and end times.

437 In this study, we do not address any specific process or sectoral application, so we do not
438 consider specific temperature thresholds or portions of the seasonal cycle particularly relevant
439 for the analysis. Instead, we assume a general definition of heatwaves as periods of at least 5
440 consecutive days during which the mean temperature over a specific area of interest is above the
441 long-term expected daily value (Hobday et al., 2016). For each test site we consider the areal
442 mean of the daily surface temperature, and we apply singular spectrum analysis method (Allen
443 and Smith 1997) to separate the slowest and smoothest components of the signal from the noisy
444 and residual fluctuations on time scales ranging from a few days to less than six-months.

445 In doing so, the dependence on time is omitted and the sea surface temperature SST can be
446 decomposed in the following terms:

447

$$448 \quad \text{SST} = \text{SST}_C + \text{SST}_T + \text{SST}_S + \text{SST}_R \quad 5)$$

449

450 where SST_C is the mean temperature during the historical period, thus representing the current
451 climate; SST_T is the long-term (i.e. multidecadal) trend component; SST_S is the periodic
452 component of the signal, typically composed of a strong annual cycle and a weaker 6-month
453 cycle; SST_R represents the residual fluctuations on shorter time scales.

454 The first step in the assessment of the ENEA-REG performances in producing the heatwaves, is
455 therefore to examine the distribution of the residuals by looking at the moments of their
456 distribution in the case of the historical and hindcast simulations that can be directly compared
457 with observation, as reported in Table 2.

458 For the mean, standard deviation and kurtosis there is no relevant improvement when comparing
459 the global driver MPI-ESM1-2-HR with the regional climate model. Fluctuations are obviously
460 distributed around a mean value of 0 °C (not shown in Table 2) and both the regional and the

461 global climate models tend to underestimate the standard deviation of the SST_R component. The
462 average value of the kurtosis is slightly larger than 3 for all three datasets, implying a larger
463 population of the tails of the distribution compared to normal distribution. However, no relevant
464 differences emerge between the global driver and the regional downscaling compared to the
465 observations.

466 Instead, more interesting, differences emerge when considering the skewness in the comparison
467 between MPI-ESM1-2-HR, its regional downscaling with ENEA-REG and the corresponding
468 hindcast simulation driven by ERA5. The skewness describes the asymmetries in the distribution
469 of SST_R, whereby positive (negative) skewness implies a prevalence of warm (cold) anomalies in
470 the fluctuations. As a first example, in the Alboran Sea, the observed fluctuations are
471 characterized by a slightly negative skewness (-0.1 °C) , and therefore by the prevalence of cold
472 anomalies, which are likely linked to the ingression of relatively colder Atlantic waters into the
473 Mediterranean, a feature of the oceanic circulation that the regional coupled model is able to
474 capture whereas the global model does not have the appropriate spatial resolution to describe the
475 process. In fact, while the skewness of the global driver is 0.3 °C (prevalence of warm
476 fluctuations), the historical simulation produces an improvement with a slightly negative
477 skewness (approximated in Table 2 with 0 °C), whereas the hindcast has a skewness of -0.2 °C.

478 Another interesting example is the case of the site north of Crete (CRETE-N) where MPI-ESM1-
479 2-HR is characterized by an excess of cold fluctuation, likely associated to larger scale
480 atmospheric winds blowing from the north, whereas the skewness for observations is 0.2 °C
481 (warm anomalies), correctly reproduced by the regional climate model, both in the hindcast and
482 in the historical simulations.

483 Other local improvements can be highlighted in the Gulf of Lion, in the Tyrrhenian Sea and in
484 the central Adriatic (ADRIATIC-C). In these cases, which are characterized by localized ocean
485 circulation patterns driven by larger scale atmospheric dynamical forcing, the global model
486 shows a symmetric distribution of the fluctuations whereas observations are characterized by a
487 prevalence of warm anomalies, which are correctly described by the regional model.

488 Although the improvements in the statistics of the residual fluctuations are not uniform over all
489 the considered sites, and a few counter examples are also reported in Table 2, the examples
490 discussed above highlight the added value of using a higher resolution ocean component in
491 describing the impact of local dynamics on shorter-time scale fluctuations.

492

493

494 **4. Future scenarios: implications for selected impacts**

495 In the following sections, we present relevant outcomes from the simulations performed with the
496 ENEA-REG in terms of projected changes in ECV and EOVs; besides, we also describe the
497 changes in occurrence and characteristics of marine heat waves in the three different analyzed
498 scenarios.

499 Considering the overall behavior of the three scenarios simulations, Figure 10 shows the
500 temporal evolution of annual near-surface air temperature and sea surface temperature averaged
501 over the entire Mediterranean basin (sea only) as simulated by ENEA-REG, along with
502 corresponding global driver simulations and observational datasets for reference.

503 In the historical period, the ENEA-REG hindcast simulation seems to slightly amplify the
504 relative minimum in SST of 2004-2005 values (García-Monteiro et al 2022) after the heat wave
505 in 2003. After this event, the oceanic component of the model exhibits a cold bias (see Figure
506 10b) also present, but weaker, in 2m temperature (Figure 10a). This feature has been already
507 highlighted by Ruti et al. (2016) for the first releases of Med-CORDEX coupled simulations, and,
508 more recently, in Storto et al. (2023).

509 Looking at the future projections, results highlight how the different scenarios are quite close in
510 the first half of XXI century, then they tend to diverge after 2050 with a difference at the end of
511 the century between SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5 of around 2 °C. In addition, an overall agreement
512 can be observed between the regional simulations and corresponding global drivers, although the
513 downscaling experiments show a weaker magnitude of the trend in the scenarios SSP2-4.5 and
514 SSP5-8.5 for both air surface temperature and SST, while, consistent with the global forcing, no
515 relevant warming is simulated in the scenario SSP1-2.6.

516

517 **4.1 Projected changes in relevant atmospheric ECVs**

518 Figure 11 shows the spatial patterns of the air surface temperature change for the three scenario
519 simulations between the end of XXI century and the historical period. Consistently with most of
520 the globe (Tebaldi et al. 2021), the warming over the Mediterranean region is projected to be
521 much larger over land than over the sea. Generally, the most relevant changes are experienced in
522 the summer season under the SSP5-8.5 with projected mean warming up to 5 °C in the Iberian
523 Peninsula and North Africa. Over Tyrrhenian Sea and in the eastern Mediterranean basin surface
524 air temperature is projected to increase up to 2.5 °C, while in the Adriatic an increase of 4°C is
525 expected to be reached during SON. During winter, temperatures tend to increase mostly over
526 Eastern Europe. The SSP2-4.5 displays a quite similar spatial patterns compared to SSP5-8.5, but

527 with a weaker warming of about 1.5°C, on average. Finally, according to the SSP1-2.6, in the
528 Euro-Mediterranean domain only few areas (Eastern Europe in winter and northern Africa in
529 summer) could experience a project warming up to 2°C.

530 Looking at changes in the mean precipitation (Figure 12), the ENEA-REG simulates a strong
531 rainfall reduction over Mediterranean basin mainly in SSP5-8.5 and SSP2-4.5 and for all the
532 seasons, while in the SSP1-2.6 the largest decrease in the Euro-Mediterranean region is found in
533 SON. Besides a common pattern is observed between the three scenarios: in particular, during
534 summer, mean precipitation tends to generally reduce, mostly in the western part of the domain
535 and over Balkan peninsula, while during winter and partially in spring more precipitation is
536 projected in the central and western Europe.

537 The above reported features for mean air surface temperature and precipitation are fully
538 consistent to what already reported in the last IPCC report (IPCC 2022). Furthermore,
539 considering the annual mean trends instead of the seasonal values showed in Figure 11 and 12,
540 our results are fully in line to what reported by Zittis et al. (2019).

541

542 **4.2 Projected changes in relevant EOVs**

543 Looking at the oceanic component of ENEA-REG, in Tables 3 and 4 we present the changes in
544 temperature and salinity profiles for the three scenario simulations between the end of XXI
545 century and the historical period. We focus on two 20-year periods (2046-2065; 2081-2100) to
546 highlight mid-term and long-term changes with respect to the reference historical simulation.

547 At mid-century, the average positive temperature anomalies over the whole Mediterranean basin
548 increase with the severity of the scenario in the surface and intermediate layers, reaching a
549 maximum of about 1°C. Anomalies in the deepest layer are smaller, and almost independent on
550 the scenario. Results also point out a difference between the main sub-basins, with markedly
551 higher surface anomalies in the eastern sub-basin, and higher intermediate anomalies in the
552 western sub-basin. The latter may reflect the downward propagation of the local surface heat
553 surplus, but inflow of warmer Levantine Intermediate Water (LIW) from the eastern
554 Mediterranean could also contribute. As for salinity, the anomalies are negative in the upper
555 layer and positive in the others, indicating a stronger stratification of the water column.

556 At the end of century, temperature anomalies over the Mediterranean basin generally increase at
557 all levels for all scenarios, except for a slight decrease in the upper layer of SSP1-2.6. The
558 strongest increase is for the SSP5-8.5 scenario, where anomalies are more than doubled with
559 respect to the mid-term period in the surface and intermediate layers (the maximum anomaly in

560 the eastern upper layer reaches 2.6°C). This is consistent with Figure 10, which shows that,
561 starting from 2060, the rate of increase of the basins SST becomes much stronger for this
562 scenario. The salinity differences vary among scenarios, displaying the greatest negative values
563 in the upper layer of the western sub-basin, indicating a growing effect of the fresher Atlantic
564 Water (AW) inflow.

565 The estimate of global mean sea level change under future scenarios has been presented in the
566 IPCC report (Fox-Kemper et al. 2021), based on about 40 CMIP6 global coupled simulations.
567 The main contribution to the sea level change is represented by thermal expansion, that is
568 computed as a global mean for each model. The other processes, including the melting of sea ice
569 in the Arctic and Antarctic Oceans, the loss of mass from glaciers, the contribution of the change
570 in land water storage and the vertical land motion have been computed by means of specific
571 models in dedicated intercomparison projects.

572 Figure 13 shows the total sea level change, averaged over the Mediterranean basin, and
573 computed from the AR6 models, for the three analyzed scenarios. The global projections and
574 confidence levels are relative to the baseline period 1995-2014; total values obtained using the
575 MPI-ESM1-2-HR and the ENEA-REG are also shown. Results highlight how both the driving
576 global model and the regional simulations are close to the ensemble's median. Besides, sea level
577 height increases when going from SSP1-2.6 to SSP5-8.5. The major difference with respect to
578 the AR6 median is found at the end of the period in the most severe scenario when the MPI-
579 ESM1-2-HR and ENEA-REG means are about 10 cm lower than the AR6.

580 A deeper insight into the sea level change under the three scenarios is shown in Figure 14 where
581 are presented sea level patterns due only to the circulation component, averaged over the last 5
582 years of the simulations (2096-2100) relative to the 1995-2014 historical period. In general, the
583 patterns of the global driving model are smoother than the regional model; for instance, the east-
584 west difference that is only slightly perceptible in the MPI-ESM1-2-HR simulations is intensified
585 in the regional ones for all the three scenarios. While the global model is virtually uniform in the
586 eastern area, in all scenarios the regional model shows an extensive area of negative values in the
587 central part of the basin and positive values along the corresponding shores.

588 Under the most severe scenario, the maximum around the Balearic Islands ranges from about 10
589 cm in the global model to 30 cm in the regional ones and the negative values covering the entire
590 Adriatic Sea in MPI-ESM1-2-HR correspond to higher values in ENEA-REG.

591 Due to the concentration of population in Mediterranean coastal zones, the extreme sea level
592 heights reached along the coast represent one of the major impacts of future scenarios. Thus, we

593 present in Figure 15 the monthly mean values near three of the main Italian ports (Genoa, Naples,
594 and Venice) derived from the global and regional simulations, while mean and standard
595 deviations are in Table 5. Except for Venice under the SSP1-2.6 scenario, all the means
596 computed for the regional model are slightly lower than for the driving GCM. Results suggest
597 that the general increase in the variability of local sea level can result in higher extreme events in
598 the regional simulation.

599

600 **4.3 Projected impact in future scenarios: implication for heat waves**

601 To illustrate the potential application of high-resolution SST fluctuations in the description of
602 localized marine heatwaves for impact studies, in the following analysis we consider the SST
603 components

604

$$605 \quad \text{SST}_{T,R} = \text{SST}_T + \text{SST}_R \quad 6)$$

606

607 representing the combined effect of the short-term fluctuations and of the long-term tendency in
608 determining the onset of marine heatwaves. In particular, we define heatwaves as periods during
609 which $\text{SST}_{T,R}$ is above a certain threshold for a period longer than 5 days.

610 As an example, Figure 16 shows the maximum intensity and total annual duration of marine
611 heatwaves in the central Adriatic. Over this area, the regional climate model is expected to
612 improve the description of temperature variability, especially during summer, when local
613 processes in the atmosphere are more relevant, as well as during fall. The figure is constructed by
614 progressively shifting the heatwave threshold from the 95-th percentile to the maximum value of
615 the model $\text{SST}_{T,R}$ over the historical period (vertical axis). Therefore, the height of the vertical
616 bars represents the maximum intensity of the heatwaves during each year; colors are associated
617 to the sum of the durations of all heatwaves during the same calendar year.

618 The initial part of the time series, until 2014, is identical for the three scenarios as it is derived
619 from the same historical simulation. For the following years, Figure 16 shows the time series of
620 marine heatwaves for the three scenarios simulated with the regional climate model ENEA-REG
621 (a), and with the corresponding global model driver MPI-ESM1-2-HR (b).

622 During the historical period, sporadic marine heatwaves appear in the time series. The intensity
623 is approximately uniform, with a mild tendency to increase frequency between 1980 and 2014.

624 A key result emerging from the comparison between the three scenarios is the different behavior
625 between SSP1-2.6 and the other two scenarios SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5. In the scenario SSP1-2.6,

626 marine heatwaves stabilize during the second half of the century in intensity, frequency and
627 duration. In this scenario, the marine heatwave maximum intensity by the end of the century is
628 comparable with the intensity detected in the historical simulation. Instead, for the scenarios
629 SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5, the intensity, frequency and duration of heatwaves continue to increase
630 until the end of the century. Besides, in the scenario SSP5-8.5, the total annual length of marine
631 heatwave increases from a few days during the initial period to virtually the entire annual cycle
632 by the end of the simulation in 2100. In other words, anomalies of up to 2°C which are
633 considered extreme (i.e. above the 95-th percentile) at the beginning of the century, will become
634 the norm in less than a hundred years under the SSP5-8.5 scenario. Such a difference between
635 the SSP1-2.6 and the other two scenarios occurs for all the areas listed in Table 2 (not shown).
636 In the specific case of the central Adriatic, the global model tends to underestimate the frequency
637 of heatwaves during the historical period and to overestimate the duration and intensity in the
638 scenarios. Along with the improved model variability in this area, as described in Figure 4, and
639 the improved statistics of fluctuations reported in Table 2, this result suggests that the description
640 of marine heatwaves may benefit from the use of higher resolution coupling, especially over
641 enclosed sub-basins.

642

643 **5. Summary and conclusions**

644 We presented an improved version of a regional ESM designed to represent the present and
645 future climate variability over the Euro-Mediterranean basin, a well-known hot-spot region for
646 climate change (Giorgi 2006). Then, we evaluated the performances of individual model
647 components comparing results, for the present climate, from hindcast (i.e. ERA5-driven) and
648 historical (i.e. GCMs-driven) simulations against the state-of-the-art of observational and
649 reanalysis datasets.

650 Overall, results indicated that the atmospheric component of the regional ESM simulates
651 reasonably well the main spatio-temporal characteristics of the analyzed essential climate
652 variables (temperature and precipitation), with precipitation not showing any relevant bias.
653 Considering the surface air temperature, compared to the first ENEA-REG version (Anav et al.
654 2021) we substantially improved the performances of the hindcast simulation: in particular,
655 summer warm bias over the whole continental Europe (except Spain), exceeding the 4 °C at
656 some locations, was considerably reduced. Similarly, the cold bias occurring in North-Eastern
657 Europe during winter has noticeably decreased in magnitude. The improved performances during
658 summer mostly depended on the differences in the parameterization used to represent the

659 microphysics; in particular, the updated microphysics scheme leads to a remarkable reduction in
660 the summer dry bias, consequently part of the surface heat flux is converted into latent heat,
661 reducing thus the surface warming. On the other side, the cold winter bias is quite common for
662 WRF simulations covering the European area and it mainly depends on the poor representation
663 of the snow–atmosphere interaction, amplified by the albedo feedback (e.g., Mooney et al. 2013;
664 Kotlarski et al. 2014; García-Díez et al. 2015; Katragkou et al. 2015). The reduced winter cold
665 bias over North-Eastern Europe can be explained by the optimization of some snow cover
666 parameters, within the updated WRF release, which could have improved the model’s
667 performance in simulating snow water equivalent, snow depth, and surface albedo.

668 At the same time, the performances of the ocean model have improved. For instance, for the
669 surface salinity we find smaller biases with respect to the previous ENEA-REG version, while
670 looking at the sea surface temperature, the summer warm bias ($> 2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) in the Tyrrhenian and
671 Sardinian Sea disappeared and the bias generally remains within $\pm 1\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

672 The improved performance of the ocean component of the regional ESM can be explained by a
673 more reliable prescription of the boundary conditions at the Atlantic box; in addition, the
674 improved performances of the atmospheric component also contribute to reduce the bias of the
675 ocean model.

676 Considering the simulated future climate, a general warming of the Mediterranean Sea with
677 respect to the present is projected under all the scenarios in terms of both air surface temperature
678 and SST. A stable positive trend is observed under SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5, while SSP1-2.6
679 induces a more limited warming up to mid-century, to then reverse such tendency and stabilize
680 around a moderate increase of about 0.7°C for both the ocean and the atmosphere, highlighting
681 how the inertia of the climate system is expected to anyway shadow the benefits of climate
682 action for a few decades ahead. An overall agreement can be observed between the regional
683 simulations and corresponding global driver, although the downscaling experiments tend to
684 underestimate the trends.

685 Looking at precipitation, the ENEA-REG foresees a relevant reduction for the mean precipitation
686 over Mediterranean basin mainly in SSP5-8.5 and SSP2-4.5, consistently to what already
687 reported in IPCC AR6 WG1 (Fox-Kemper et al. 2021).

688 The Mediterranean dynamic sea level (i.e. the component due to the circulation) increases for all
689 scenarios, more conspicuously under SSP5-8.5 and SSP2-4.5. Both spatial and temporal
690 variability are enhanced in the regional simulations with respect to the global projections, which
691 might have a non-negligible impact on coastal risk assessments.

692 Regarding the representation of marine heatwaves, we have highlighted the potential advantage
693 of using a higher resolution ocean component in describing the impact of local dynamics on
694 shorter-time scale fluctuations, especially over enclosed sub-basins such as the Adriatic Sea. Our
695 results suggest that the intensity, frequency, and duration of marine heat waves will continue to
696 increase until the end of the century for the scenarios SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5, whereas for SSP1-
697 2.6 they stabilize after the first half of the century, coherently with the overall trend. In particular,
698 anomalies of up to 2°C which are considered extreme (i.e. above the 95-th percentile) at the
699 beginning of the century, will become the norm in less than a hundred year for the SSP5-8.5
700 scenario, thereby implying potential severe impacts on ecosystems, on ecosystem services and on
701 local communities and on the broader Mediterranean economy.

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1022

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1024 The authors of this paper have no relevant financial or non-financial interests to disclose.

1025

1026 **Author Contributions**

1027 All authors discussed the results and contributed to the writing of the article; Alessandro Anav
1028 performed the simulations.

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		Depth (m)		
		0-150	150-600	600-3500
		TEMPERATURE		
MED	Reanalysis	16,65	14,05	13,35
	Hindcast	0,09	0,25	0,27
	Historical	-0,04	0,33	0,25
WMED	Reanalysis	15,41	13,46	12,96
	Hindcast	0,43	0,30	0,15
	Historical	0,15	0,25	0,13
EMED	Reanalysis	17,33	14,41	13,57
	Hindcast	-0,08	0,21	0,36
	Historical	-0,12	0,38	0,34
		SALINITY		
MED	Reanalysis	38,41	38,82	38,66
	Hindcast	0,18	0,02	0,12
	Historical	0,15	0,04	0,11
WMED	Reanalysis	37,85	38,50	38,48
	Hindcast	0,04	0,04	0,03
	Historical	-0,01	0,02	0,02
EMED	Reanalysis	38,73	38,85	38,81
	Hindcast	0,22	0,17	0,12
	Historical	0,22	0,21	0,12

1050 **Table 1.** Average Temperature (°C) and Salinity (psu) at various depths for the whole
1051 Mediterranean (MED), the Western (WMED) and the Eastern (EMED) sub-basins. The first-row
1052 reports averages from the Copernicus Reanalysis dataset, the second and third rows report
1053 differences between the hindcast and the historical simulations with respect to the reanalysis. All
1054 spatial averages are taken over the period 1987-2014.

	Standard Deviation						Skewness				Kurtosis			
	LON	LAT	OBS	HIN	MPI	REG	OBS	HIN	MPI	REG	OBS	HIN	MPI	REG
ALBORAN	-3	36	0.9	0.6	0.7	0.6	-0.1	-0.2	0.3	0.0	4.0	3.8	4.6	3.6
LION	4	42	1.0	0.7	0.8	0.7	0.3	0.3	0.0	0.5	4.0	4.1	3.4	4.5
LIGURIAN	9	43.5	1.0	0.8	0.7	0.8	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	4.5	4.3	3.9	4.7
SICILY	11.5	38	0.8	0.7	0.6	0.6	0.1	0.0	0.3	0.3	3.5	4.3	3.9	3.9
TIRRENIAN	11.5	41	0.9	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.3	0.1	0.1	0.3	4.2	3.7	3.8	3.9
IONIAN-W	12.5	35.5	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.3	3.3	4.1	3.5	4.1
LAMPEDUSA	13	44.5	0.8	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.2	0.1	0.1	0.3	3.6	3.7	3.7	3.5
ADRIATIC-N	16.5	42.5	1.1	0.8	0.9	0.9	0.3	0.0	0.0	0.0	3.8	2.9	3.0	2.8
ADRIATIC-S	16.5	37	0.9	0.6	0.8	0.6	0.2	0.1	0.2	0.2	4.1	3.5	3.3	3.9
ADRIATIC-C	17	41.5	0.9	0.7	0.8	0.7	0.2	0.1	0.0	0.1	4.0	3.4	3.2	3.7
IONIAN-E	19.5	38.5	0.8	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.3	0.2	0.1	0.1	3.8	3.3	3.6	3.8
CRETE-N	24	36.2	0.8	0.5	0.7	0.6	0.2	0.1	-0.2	0.1	3.4	4.0	3.7	3.4
AEGEAN	24	34	0.9	0.6	0.8	0.6	0.0	0.0	0.1	0.1	3.7	3.7	4.0	3.5
CRETE-S	25	38.5	0.7	0.6	0.6	0.5	0.1	0.2	0.1	0.1	3.5	3.5	3.4	3.2
MARSA	27.5	32.5	0.6	0.5	0.7	0.5	-0.1	-0.1	0.1	0.0	3.3	3.1	3.1	3.3
RHODES	29	35	0.8	0.6	0.7	0.6	0.2	0.0	0.0	0.2	3.4	3.2	3.4	3.4
CYPRUS	32.5	33.5	0.7	0.5	0.7	0.5	0.0	0.2	0.0	0.2	3.3	3.1	3.0	3.1

1056

1057 **Table 2.** Standard deviation, skewness, and kurtosis of the distribution of the residual fluctuation
1058 (see section 3.3 for a definition) of the average sea surface temperature over selected areas. Each
1059 area is defined as 1° x 1° pseudo-rectangle centered around the coordinates indicated in the
1060 columns LON, LAT. OBS are the statistics derived from observations, HIN are the statistics
1061 from the hindcast simulation with ENEA-REG driven by ERA5, MPI is the historical simulation
1062 of the global model MPI-ESM1-2-HR and REG is the regional climate model ENEA-REG
1063 driven by MPI-ESM1-2-HR .

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		Depth (m)		
		0-150	150-600	600-3500
		TEMPERATURE		
MED	SSP126	0,73	0,88	0,47
	SSP245	0,85	0,97	0,45
	SSP585	1,07	1,00	0,46
WMED	SSP126	0,59	1,05	0,58
	SSP245	0,66	1,17	0,57
	SSP585	0,75	1,18	0,57
EMED	SSP126	0,81	0,79	0,40
	SSP245	0,95	0,85	0,37
	SSP585	1,25	0,89	0,39
		SALINITY		
MED	SSP126	-0,11	0,19	0,17
	SSP245	-0,10	0,18	0,13
	SSP585	-0,14	0,14	0,13
WMED	SSP126	-0,22	0,23	0,16
	SSP245	-0,24	0,23	0,14
	SSP585	-0,28	0,20	0,14
EMED	SSP126	-0,05	0,16	0,17
	SSP245	-0,02	0,14	0,12
	SSP585	-0,06	0,10	0,13

1067

1068 **Table 3.** Differences between values averaged over the period 2046–2065 of the three scenarios
1069 and the whole period (1985–2014) of the historical simulation. Averages are computed over the
1070 whole Mediterranean Sea (MED), and over the western and eastern sub-basins (WMED and
1071 EMED)

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		Depth (m)		
		0-150	150-600	600-3500
		TEMPERATURE		
MED	SSP126	0,61	0,91	0,66
	SSP245	1,05	1,11	0,61
	SSP585	2,45	2,08	0,68
WMED	SSP126	0,46	1,12	0,84
	SSP245	0,92	1,47	0,84
	SSP585	2,16	2,40	0,88
EMED	SSP126	0,70	0,78	0,55
	SSP245	1,12	0,89	0,46
	SSP585	2,62	1,89	0,56
		SALINITY		
MED	SSP126	-0,15	0,08	0,18
	SSP245	-0,27	0,06	0,15
	SSP585	-0,06	0,22	0,16
WMED	SSP126	-0,21	0,16	0,19
	SSP245	-0,38	0,19	0,18
	SSP585	-0,27	0,33	0,18
EMED	SSP126	-0,12	0,03	0,17
	SSP245	-0,21	-0,01	0,13
	SSP585	0,06	0,16	0,15

1075

1076 **Table 4.** Differences between values averaged over period 2081–2100 of the three scenarios and
1077 the whole period (1981–2014) of the historical simulation. Averages are computed over the
1078 whole Mediterranean Sea (MED), and over the western and eastern sub-basins (WMED and
1079 EMED)

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Site	scenario	MPI-ES-1-2-HR (cm)	ENEA-REG (cm)
GENOA	SSP1-2.6	3.1 ± 4.5	1.6 ± 6.6
	SSP2-4.5	3.6 ± 4.8	2.4 ± 6.1
	SSP5-8.5	3.0 ± 4.9	2.2 ± 6.3
VENICE	SSP1-2.6	2.4 ± 6.0	0.7 ± 8.5
	SSP2-4.5	0.7 ± 6.1	0.8 ± 7.9
	SSP5-8.5	0.9 ± 6.6	0.9 ± 7.8
NAPLES	SSP1-2.6	3.0 ± 4.0	1.5 ± 6.8
	SSP2-4.5	3.4 ± 4.0	2.2 ± 6.3
	SSP5-8.5	2.7 ± 4.3	1.8 ± 6.4

1083

1084 **Table 5.** Comparison of sea level height mean and standard deviation for the three scenarios on
1085 model points near to Genoa, Naples, and Venice. Values are computed with respect to the
1086 average over the 1995-2014 historical period.

1087

1089
 1090 **Figure 1.** Domain used for the ENEA-REG simulations; the area defined by the black solid line
 1091 represents the computational domain of the atmospheric model, with green shading highlighting
 1092 the topography. The ocean domain is defined by the blue shading, used to represent bathymetry.
 1093 Black boxes indicate seven regions, defined in the frame of the PRUDENCE project
 1094 (Christensen and Christensen, 2007), which are widely used for evaluation of climate models
 1095 over Europe; they are: the Alps (AL), the British Isles (BI), Eastern Europe (EA), France (FR),
 1096 the Iberian Peninsula (IP), the Mediterranean (MD), and Mid-Europe (ME).

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1101 **Figure 2.** Mean seasonal (winter, spring, summer, and fall) near-surface air temperature spatially
 1102 averaged over the PRUDENCE regions from: reference data (ERA5, black boxes), the ENEA-
 1103 REG hindcast (blue boxes) and historical simulations (green boxes), the driving model of the
 1104 historical experiment (i.e. MPI-ESM1-2-HR, red boxes) and the ensemble mean of 25 CMIP6
 1105 models (gray circle). The orange lines within the boxes represent the median of the temperature
 1106 while the yellow circles are used to indicate the mean value. The seasonal averages are computed
 1107 over the period 1982–2014.

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1110 **Figure 3.** Centered pattern correlation between the surface air temperature from the reference
 1111 data (i.e ERA5) and the ENEA-REG hindcast (blue boxes) and historical simulations (green
 1112 boxes); besides, we also show the pattern correlation for MPI-ESM1-2-HR (red boxes) which
 1113 has been used to drive the historical experiment. The seasonal patterns are computed for the
 1114 reference period 1982-2014 over the PRUDENCE sub-regions (Christensen and Christensen,
 1115 2007). In this analysis the two WRF experiments, and the global MPI-ESM1-2-HR model have
 1116 been regridded to the ERA5 grid. 1% level significance of pattern correlation difference between
 1117 the historical and the hindcast simulation (gray circles) and between the historical and the global
 1118 model simulation (gray stars) has been assessed by bootstrap procedure with 1000 repetitions.

1119

1120 **Figure 4.** Model Variability Index (MVI) of near-surface air temperature for the ENEA_REG
 1121 hindcast simulation (left column), the ENEA-REG historical simulation (central column) and the
 1122 MPI-ESM1-2-HR simulation (right column). Boreal winter DJF (first row), spring MAM
 1123 (second row), summer JJA (third row), autumn SON (fourth row).

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Figure 5. As **Figure 2**, but for precipitation.

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Figure 6. As **Figure 3**, but for precipitation.

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1135 **Figure 7.** Model Variability Index (MVI) of Precipitation for the ENEA-REG hindcast
 1136 simulation (left column), the ENEA-REG historical simulation (central column) and the MPI-
 1137 ESM1-2-HR simulation (right column). Boreal winter DJF (first row), spring MAM (second
 1138 row), summer JJA (third row), autumn SON (fourth row).

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1143 **Figure 8.** Comparison of seasonal sea surface temperature from satellite data, the ENEA-REG

1144 hindcast and historical experiments and the MPI-ESM1-2-HR model. Seasonal averages are

1145 computed for the period 1982–2014.

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1151 **Figure 9.** The maps show the average sea level as simulated by the hindcast and historical
 1152 experiments (1982–2014 average) and the satellite observations (1993-2014 average). The
 1153 average circulation at 30 m of depth has been superimposed on the elevation in the two ENEA-
 1154 REG simulations, while a geostrophic reconstruction of the circulation has been used in the case
 1155 of the MDT (also provided by CMEMS). In the top left panel, the annual time series of the
 1156 average basin elevation from the hindcast (black dots) is compared with that resulting from the
 1157 observations (red dots).

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 1159 **Figure 10.** Annual time series of near-surface air temperature (a) and Sea Surface temperature
 1160 (b) (°C) from the ENEA-REG scenario simulations averaged over the entire Mediterranean basin.

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1167 **Figure 11.** Near-surface air temperature (K) projected climate change (2071-2100 minus 1985-
 1168 2014) from the ENEA-REG scenario simulations: SSP1-2.6 (left column), SSP2-4.5 (central
 1169 column) and SSP5-8.5 (right column). Boreal winter DJF (first row), spring MAM (second row),
 1170 summer JJA (third row), autumn SON (fourth row). Values at all grid points are significant at
 1171 10% level. Significance assessed by bootstrap procedure with 1000 repetitions.

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1174 **Figure 12.** Precipitation (mm d-1) projected climate change (2071-2100 minus 1985-2014) from
 1175 the ENEA-REG scenario simulations: SSP1-2.6 (left column), SSP2-4.5 (central column) and
 1176 SSP5-8.5 (right column). Boreal winter DJF (first row), spring MAM (second row), summer JJA
 1177 (third row), autumn SON (fourth row). Black dots indicate 10% level significance, assessed by
 1178 bootstrap procedure with 1000 repetitions.

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1185 **Figure 13** –Change of the average total sea level over the Mediterranean basin for the three SSP
 1186 scenarios (blue curves; dotted=MPI-ESM1-2-HR; dashed=ENE-REG). The projections are
 1187 relative to a 1995-2014 baseline. The thick red line is the median over the AR6 models and the
 1188 shaded area corresponds to the 17th-83rd percentile range.

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1202 **Figure 14** – Sea surface height computed averaging the last five years of the simulations respect
 1203 to the average over the historical period 1995-2014. Left panels for the MPI-ESM1-2-HR model,
 1204 right panels ENEA-REG simulations. Only the circulation component is considered.

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1213 **Figure 15** – Comparison of the MPI-ESM1-2-HR (MPI) and ENEA-REG sea surface height for
 1214 model points near to Genoa, Naples and Venice. From the left to the right column, scenario
 1215 SSP1-2.6, SSP2-4.5 and SSP5-8.5. Monthly values and yearly means are shown. Values are
 1216 computed with respect to the average over the 1995-2014 historical period.

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ENEA-REG - ADRIATIC-C

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(a)

(b)

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 1223 **Figure 16.** Intensity and total annual length of heatwaves for the central Adriatic as described by
 1224 ENEA-REG (a) and by the global driver MPI-ESM1-2-HR. The thresholds for the identification
 1225 of heatwaves are set between the 95-th percentile and the maximum value of the corresponding
 1226 daily temperature anomalies w/r to the local seasonal cycle during the historical period (1980-
 1227 2014). Heatwaves are defined as periods of at least 5 consecutive days with temperature anomaly
 1228 above the threshold.

Supplementary MATERIAL

Figure S.1. Ratio of standard deviation relative to reanalysis of near-surface air temperature for the ENEA_REG hindcast simulation (left column), the ENEA-REG historical simulation (central column) and the MPI-ESM1-2-HR simulation (right column). Boreal winter DJF (first row), spring MAM (second row), summer JJA (third row), autumn SON (fourth row).

Figure S.2: Time series of annual average (1981-2014) of near-surface air temperature (left) and daily precipitation (right), spatially averaged over the PRUDENCE sub-regions.

Figure S.3: As Figure S.2, but seasonally averaged anomalies (season DJF).

Figure S.4: As Figure S.2, but seasonally averaged anomalies (season MAM).

Figure S.5: As Figure S.2, but seasonally averaged anomalies (season JJA).

Figure S.6: As Figure S.2, but seasonally averaged anomalies (season SON).